

Ancient Education System in Ennayiram

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A B S T R A C T

Various educational institutes were established and run in Chola period. For teaching Vedas in so-called higher education. Vedic colleges were also conducted here and there. Among them Most notably, the first is Rajendran (AD 1012-1044) operated in Ennayiram villages Vedic college. Chola Emperor, has gifted the 300 Acres acres for this college. All the four Vedas were taught here. In this, junior students, master students, and teachers have been there. Junior students who were celibate also studied Rupavathara grammar. Others also studied the RigVeda, YajurVeda, Vajasaneya Sama Veda, SandokaSamaVeda, TalavakaraSama Veda, AtharvaVeda, Buddhist Krishya Sutra, Buddhist Kalpa Sutra and Buddhist Gnana Sutra. Each of these junior students was given six najis daily. 70 people who are satras or master students were given ten Nazis of paddy each day.

Key Words: Vedic Education, college, Teachers, Students, Chola period.

Introduction

Ennayaram is a village near Esalam near Villupuram. Ennayaram village is proud to be the place where the Vedic College was held during the reign of Rajendra Chola I, the place where the Jain sages who gave the literature Naladiyar lived, and the birthplace of the poet Kalamegam. During the Pallavar period, this town was known as Bardhikollai and was called 'Irajaraja Chaturvedi Mangalam' after Rajaraja I during the Chola period. Not sure when it became 'eight thousand'? This village is the place where Vaishnavism flourished. An example of this is the beautiful Narasingha Perumal temple here. This temple was earlier called 'Irajaraja Vinnakar'. The temple is a testament to the Chola era architecture and has beautiful sculptures and numerous inscriptions. Here Perumal is seen lying down.

Ennayiram

Ennayiram and its surroundings known in Chola times as the Rajaraja Chadurvedi Mangalam was a place of significance during the reign of Rajaraja and later. It received considerable attention from the polity. It was also a frontier arcit, captured by the Banas and the Gangas for some time.

Rajendra I - An inscription dated in the twenty-fifth year, 112th day of Rajendra 1 (A.D. 1036), found on the west and south walls of the central shrine of Alagiya Narasimha Perumal temple, mentions that on the order of the king Rajendra 1, the assembly of Rajaraja chaturvedimangalam in Rajaraja valanadu, met in the hall called Mummudi-sola mandapam under the chairmanship of Nambi-udattur Udaiyar, who administered the village, and made arrangements regarding the allocation of the income derived from lands belonging to a number of temples, and set apart the quantities for various services in these temples.

A very important and interesting inscription found in the Alagiya Narasimha Perumal temple. belongs to Rajendra I; the date of the inscription is unfortunately so completely effaced that it is difficult to make it out, but, based on the conquests mentioned therein, it cannot be earlier than A. D.1023. By the king's order, 45 velis of land in Anangur alias Rajarajanallur was given to Rajaraja Vinnagar (Alagiyasinga Perumal temple) by the mahasabha of the taniyur of Rajaraja chaturvedimangalam (Ennayiram) for offerings, festivals, the recitation of Tiruvaymoli,

the maintenance of an institution of higher learning for teaching the Vedas, Vyakarana, Mimamsa and Vedanta.

Rajadhiraja I-On the walls of the central shrine, there is an inscription of the thirteenth year of Rajadhiraja I According to it, the Perunguri (the great assembly) of the taniyur of Rajaraja- chaturvedimangalam, a brahmadeyam in Panaiyur nadu included in Rajendra Choli valandu, met in the mandapa called Mummadi-solan with Alagan Virrizandan alias Mummadi-solan with Ala Neipendra sola Muven- davelar, the governor of the region as its President, and ordered the lands of the temple of Tiruvayppadi devar to be taxed at the lowest scale (kadai-taram), as were those of Rajaraja vinnagar devar (Alagiya Narasinga Perumal temple) and, Kurdavai vinnagar: devar (Kari Varada Perumal temple) at Dadapuram. The order of the king is said to have been passed on to the Assembly three years later."

Kulottunga I - There are seven inscriptions which are assignable to the reign of Kulottunga I. The first, of his seventh regnal year, mentions a gift of 10 cows for a lamp to the temple of Rajaraja Vinagar Alvar at Rajaraja-chaturvedimangalam by Ulagalandan Tiruvarangadevan of Kulattur, evidently the officer entrusted with the work of land survey.

Alagiya Narasimha Perumal Temple

The temple at Ennayiram known as Alagiya Narasimha Perumal temple has some valuable inscriptions that throw light on the administrative arrangements that existed then; and there is one record in particular that gives us valuable details about a Vedic College and a hostel runs in the campus of the temple. The temple is facing east with a balipeedam and an empty mandapam. In the sanctum Sri Azhagiya Lakshmi Narasimhar and Mahalakshmi is sitting of the left lap in thirumana (marriage) posture. In front of Lakshmi Narasimhar Sridevi & Bhudevi samedha Sri Vaikundha Perumal. In the artha mandapam Lakshmi Varaha. Varahar's face turned to left and narrates the Varaha purana to Mahalakshmi. Originally Sri Vaikunta Perumal and Sri Lakshmi Varahar are in the first and second tiers of the Vimana. In addition to this Chathurbhuj Venugopalan, Ramanujar and Alvars are in the mandapam. There is no separate sannadhi for Thayar. The temple consists of sanctum sanctorum, antarala, artha mandapam, Maha mandapam and a Mukka mandapam. The sanctum sanctorum is constructed in an elevated level with Upanam and Padma bandha adhistanam. In munmandapam one of the pillars is of Pallava period

Squatting lion Pillar. Rajaraja Chola reconstructed this temple. Chola period inscriptions are found in adhistanam and mandapam. The inscriptions mainly speaks about donations given to the temple. As per the inscriptions about 240 acres of land was donated to this temple and now it huts only 31 acres in records. A portion of the income was deposited in the HR&CE and nothing comes to this temple directly. The temple is under the control of Archaeological Survey of India (ASI) and the renovation is in progress. It was told that there were 4 Shiva Temples constructed keeping this Lakshmi Narasingar temple at the Centre. Hence this place is called as pancha sthalam. Ramanujar defeated 8000 Jains in a debate and converted them in to Vaishnavam or Ashta Sahasra Brahmins. This is the birthplace of Kalameka poet.

Vedic College

According to the inscription of Rajendra I, relating to the setting up of a Vedic College in the temple premises (ARE 333 of 1917), the assembly made the following provisions among others four persons were appointed for the recitation of Tiruvaymoli hymns in the temple and they were allowed three kurunis of paddy each per day. To meet this charge, land at Anangur alias Rajarajanallur measuring half a veil and two main extents was given for feeding twenty-five Sri-Vaishnavas in the hermitage attached to the same temple, one veil and four ma of land in the same place were allotted. Sixty years of paddy and three kalanjus of gold were also provided for the seven-day festival of Ani-Anulam in order to feed one thousand Vaishnavas and devotees who came to witness it. Half a veli and two ma of land and some gold were given to meet the cost of taking the god in procession round the village, in a car, for the grant of clothes to the mendicants on the occasion; for purchasing cloth to be put on the deity: for offerings, bath and garlands; for performing certain ceremonies etc.

The following students were fed in the GangaikondaCholan: 75 studying the Rig Veda, 75 studying the Yajur Veda, 20 studying the Chandoga-Sama 20 studying the Talavakara-Sama, 20 studying the Vajastineya, 10 studying the Atharva, 10 studying the Baudhayaniya Grihya-kalpa and Gana Thus making a total of 230 brahmacharins for studying the above-mentioned (apurvam) Vedas which, with the 40 persons learning the Rupavatara, came to 270. Six nalis of paddy were allotted for each of these per day.

Further there were: 25 learning the Vyakaran, 35 learning the Prabhakara, and 10 persons learning the Vedanta. For these 70 pupils (sattirar) who learnt the ottu (Vedas), provision was made at the rate of one kuruni and two nalis of paddy each per day. One kalam of paddy was given to the nambi who expounded the Vyakarana, one kalam to another who expounded the Prabhakara and one kalam and one tuni to the third who expounded the Vedanta. Ten professors were appointed to teach the Vedas as detailed below: Three to teach the Rig-Veda, Three to teach the Yajur Veda , One to teach the Chandoga, One to teach the Talavakara Sama, One to teach the Vajasaneya (1) (Yajnavalkya's recension of the Yajur Veda)One to teach the Baudhayaniya grihya and kalpa and Kathaka.

The teacher who expounded the Rupavatars got three kurunis of paddy a day. Thus, for a day, 30 kalams of paddy measured by the Rajaraja-marakkal were required. The annual requirements came to 10,506 kalams of paddy. The gold required for expenses was as follows 8 kalanjus of gold to the professor of Vyakarana for expounding & adhyayas at one kalanju per adhyaya, 12 kalanjus to expounding 12 adhyayas at one kalanju per adhyaya, 6½ kalanjus to the 13 professors who taught Vedas and to the one who expounded the Rupavatara at halfa kalanju each, and 35 kalanjus at half a kalanju each, to the 70 pupils (sattirar) who learnt the Vyakarana and the Mimamsa. Thus, in all, for the 61 J kalanjus of gold and the paddy that were required, the temple was put in possession of 45 velis of land situated in Mambakkachcheri alias Pavittiramanikka- nalinforming part of Anangur alias Rajarajanallur and Melakkudalur alias Purushanarayana- nallur.

King Rajendra Choladeva I, having thus directed the assembly of Rajarajachaturvedimangalam, ordered, in the presence of Kali Ekamranar, the head of the village, that they should not show in the account books, any more taxes than 1/16 ma and one padakku against the persons residing in the said two villages and cultivating the 45 veils of land, and this they promised to do under solemn oaths. This inscription is of great importance to us as it shows clearly that in ancient temples not only was the regular conduct of worship maintained but also the study of the Vedas, philosophy. grammar and other sciences was encouraged by munificent royal grants. Gifts made for such purposes as these were known as Vedavritti and Adhyayananga. In some cases, provision was made for feeding a few persons versed in the Vedas, and Apurvins.

Hostel Facility In Vedic Period

The hostel attached to the temple at Ennayiram seems to have fed not only teachers and students of the Vedic College but other men as well. One of the records (ARE 343 of 1917) refers to the maintenance of a hostel, presumably attached to the college. Here provision was made for feeding 506 learned men among whom were Vedic scholars and Sri Vaishnavas. This number might have included the 350 attached to the college. The rest must have included those who sang the Tintppadiyam, who formed the goshti, who recited the Tiruppugal and who uttered Sadyajnam. As jatakadakshina on the day of Jayantyashtami (the birthday) of Vennai kuttar (Krishna), it is stated, those brahmanas who completed the study of the Rig. Yajur and Sama Vedas should receive a gold flower and a gold ring. On the merchant class which received money from the markets devolved the duty of supplying well-husked rice which they were enjoined to bring to the hostel and measure out at the rate of two to five of paddy for (feeding) the inmates. The great men in charge of the urvariyaam (the village Supervision Committee) had to look after the daily supply of firewood required for the hostel. The brahmana and Valanjiya merchants who traded in the south bazaar were given a certain amount of money and they agreed to supply sugar and other articles in lieu of the interest on the sum lent. And it is further added that the excess of ghee, milk and curds that remained after meeting the requirements of the temple should be made over to the hostel.

Inscriptions:

Taluk: Villupuram (South Arcot) Regnal Year:

Dynasty: Chola Historical Year: 11th Century A.D

King: Rajendra Language: Tamil Script & Grantha.

Village: Ennayiram Earlier Publication: EI-Vol. XXXIX, No. 34.

Location: On the vertical face of the base on the north side of the central shrine in the ALAGIYA NARASIMHA PERUMAL TEMPLE.

Summary

It records the provisions made by the assembly of Rajaraja Chaturvedimangalam, a brahmadeya and an independent village in Jayangonda chola mandalam in order to secure success to the arms of the king (Sri pujankal Varttikka) to the deity (Paramaswamy) who was pleased to stand with a fierce appearance in the temple of Rajarajavinnakar. The endowments were made to appoint four persons to recite Tiruvaymoli, to feed 25 srivaishnavas in the matha attached, for conducting 7 days festival in the month of Aani, the procession of the deity on that occasion, sacred cloth and offerings. It is also stated that the king RajendraChola having overthrown the rulers of northern country returned with all the splendours of the conquest. He is adorned with the title Gangaikonda Chola after the victory over Ganges and by way of celebrating it, he made the gift of 45 veli of land in Mampakkacheri alias Pavitramanikkanallur and Melkadalur alias Purushottamanallur for the maintenance of the education, teachers and students at the mandapa named 'Gangaikondacholan'. The order of the King was endorsed by the mahasabha in the presence of Kali Ekambaranar, the head of the village. In view of the importance of the information, contained in this inscription, the details are tabulated here along with the details from other such records from Tribhuvani and Tirumukkudal.

Inscriptions:

ஸ்வஸ்திஸ்ரீ மெய்க்கீர்த்தி உள்ளது கோப்பர கேசரிவன்மரான உடையார். ஸ்ரீராஜேந்திர சோழதேவற்கு மாண்டுது இலங்கொண்டசோழ மண்டலத்து பிரம்மதேயம் தனிபூர் ஸ்ரீ ராஜராஜ சதுரவேதிமங்கலத்து மஹாசபையோம் சந்திராதித்யவற் நிற்க, உடையார் ஸ்ரீராஜேந்திரசோழதேவர் ஸ்ரீபுஜங்கள் வர்த்திக்க, நம்மூர் நடுவில் திருமுற்றம்ஸ்ரீராஜராஜவி ன்னகரில் மஹாகோரமாய் எழுந்தருளி நின்று திருவாரானைகொண்டருளுகின்ற பரமல் வாமிகள் ஊருடைப் பெருமாளுக்கு.

தாங்கள் திருச்சென்னடைக்கும் திருவாய்மொழி விண்ணப்பஞ் செய்யவேண்டு நிபந்தங்க ளுக்கும் திருநுந்தாவிளக்கு இரண்டுக்கு நெய்யுரியும், அமுதுக்கு நெய் உழக்குமாக நெய் மூவுழக்குக்கு நெல்லு முக்குறுணியும், பருப்பு உள்ளிட்ட கறி அமுது நாலுக்கு நெல்லு நா னாழியும், தயிர் அமுது முந்தாழிக்கு தெல்லு முத்தாழியும், உப்பமுதுக்கு நெல்லு நாழியும்,

அடைககாலமுதுக்கு நென்று நாநாழியும், அமுதுசெய்தருள போது போது அரிசி குறுணி யாக நாள் ஒன்றுக்கு அரிசி முக்குறுணிக்கு அஞ்சிரண்டு வண்ணத்தால் எழுகுறுவரி தாநா ழியும் ஆக..க்கு கலத்துக்கும், திருவாய்மொழி விள்ளப்பஞ் செய்வார் நால்வர்க்கு, பேரால் நாள் ஒன்றுக்கு தென்று முக்குறுணிக்கு நிலம் மூன்று மாவாக நிலம் அரையே இரண்டுமா லாக நாங்கள் குடுத்த விளை நிலமாவது.

ஆனாங்கூரான ராஜராஜநல்லூரின் ஸ்ரீகேரளப்பெருவதிக்கு கிழக்கு ஸ்ரீகண்ணவய்க்காலு க்குத் தெற்கு அஞ்சாங் கண்ணாற்று முதற்சதிரம் அரையே இரண்டு மாவும் இது திருச்சென் னடைக்கு இட்ட நிலமாவது, ஆறாங்கண்ணாற்று முதற் சதிரம் அரையேயிரண்டு மாவும் ஆக நிலம் ஒன்றே நான்கு மாவும் இவ்வாழ்வார். வைத்து(ருளின மட(ம)த்தில் உண்ணும் ஸ்ரீவைவிண்ணவர் இருபத்தைவ்வர்க்கு இட்ட நிலமாவது, இவ்வாறாவ் கண்ணாற்று இரு ண்டாஞ் சதிரம் அரையே இரண்டு மாவும் அஞ்சாங் கண்ணாற்று இரண்டாஞ் சதிரம் அ ரையே இரண்டு மாவும் ஆக மடப்புறம் ஒன்றே நான்கு மாலம்.

இவ்வாழ்வார்.ஆனி அனிமுத்திருநாளுக்கு திருக்கொடிப்புடவையள்ளிட்ட அற்றைநாள்வ ரை அழிவுக்குப் பொன்கழஞ்சம், திருவிளக்கெண்ணை நாள் ஏழுக்கு பொன் இரு கழஞ்சம், இந்தாளில் சேவிக்கும் வையின்ன வர்க்கும், தாதர்களுக்கும் ஆக உண்பார் ஆயிரவர்க்கு நாள் ஏழுக்கு நெல் அறுபதின் கலமும், இவ்வாழ்வார் கிராமபிரதக்ஷினத்துக்குத் திருத்தே ர் ஏறி அருளுநார் இயாசகர்க்கு தியாகத்துக்கும் பிரசாதிக்கும் பரிசட்டங் கருக்கும் பொ ன் ஐங்கழஞ்சம், சாத்தியருளு திருப்பரி சட்டம் இரண்டுக்கு பொன் கழஞ்சம் உற்சலத்து ஐ ந்து பெருந்திருவமுதுக்கும் உத்தமபடிக்குத் திருமஞ்சனத்துக்கும் பொன் அரைக்கழஞ்சம், திருப்பள்ளித் தாமத்துக்குப் பொன் அரைக் கழஞ்சம் ஆக இத்திருபிரஸ்தத்துக்கு கொண்ட ருளின் நிலம், இவ்வாறாங் கண்ணாற்று மூன்றாஞ் சதுரம் அரையே விரண்டு மாவும்,

இவ்வூருடைப் பெருமாள் முன்பமுது செய்தருளுகிறபடி பங்கு நாலில் அரிசி குறுணி நாநாழி ஏற்றி போது குறுணி தாநாழியாக அரிசி தூணி நானழியும், வீற்றிருந்தார்க்கு பங்கு ஐஞ்ச ம், தேசாத்திரிகளுக்கு பங்கு நான்நாளுக்கு போது அரிசி நாதாழி அமுது செய்தருளவும், இ வ்வூரிலிப் பெருமாள் உடையார் ஸ்ரீராஜேந்திரசோழதேவர் உத்தர பத(ரு) பூபதியரை ஐய

த்தருளி யுத்தோச்சன விபவத்தாய் கங்(க்ரா) காபண்ணி யருளின் கங்கைகொண்டசோழன் என்னும் திருநாமத்தால் இத்திருமுற் நத்தின்லைத்தருளின் உத்தமாக்கரம் கங்கைகொண்ட சோழநில் உண்ணும் அனைத்து வேதமும் அபூர்வமும் ஒதும் பிரம்மச்சாரிகளில், ரிக் வேதம் ஒதுவார் எழுபத்தைஞ்சும், யஜுர் வேதம் ஒதுவார் எழுபத்தைஞ்சும், சந்தோகார சாமத்துக்கு இருபதும், தவைகார சாமத்துக்கு இருபதும், வாஜசனையத் துக்கு இருபதும், அதர்வத்துக்கு பத்தும், பௌதாயநியம் க்ருஹ்ய கல்பமும் காடகமும் ஒதுவார்க்கு பத்தும், அபூர்வம் ஒதும் பிரம்மச்சாரிகள் இருநூற்று முப்பதின்மரும், ருபாவதாரம் கேட்பார் நாற்பதின்மரும். ஆக இருநூற்று எழுபதின்மர்க்குக் கலம் ஒன்றினுக்கு நெல்லு அறுநாழியும்.

வ்யாகரணம் கேட்பார் இருபத்தைஞ்சும், ப்ரபாகரம் கேட்பார் முப்பதி தைஞ்சும் வேதாந்தம கேட்பார் பதின்மராக ஒத்துக் கேட்கும் சாத்ரகள் எழுபதுக்கம் கலம் ஒன்றிலுக்கு நெல்லுக் குறுணி இருநாழியும், வியாகரணம் வக்காணிக்கும் நம்பிக்கு நாள் ஒன்றுக்கு நெல்லுக் கலமும் ப்ரபாகரம் வக்காணிப்பார் ஒருத்தரிக்கு நெல்லு சுலனே தூணியும், வேதம் அபூர்வம் ஒது விப்பார். ரிக்வேதத்துக்கு மூவரும், யஜுர் வேதத்துக்கு மூவரும்

சாந்தோகசாமத்துக்கு ஒருவனும் தலைகார சாமத்துக்கு ஒருவனும், வாஜானேயத்துக்கு ஒருவனும், பௌதாயநிய ஸ்ருஹ்யமும் கல்பமும் காடகமும் ஒதுளிப்பால் ஒருவனுக்கும் ஆக ஒதுளிப்பார் உபாதியாம். ருபாவதாரம் வக்காணிப்பால் ஒருவனுக்கு நெல்லு முக்குறுணியும் ஆக நாள் ஒன்றுக்கு நெல்லு ஸ்ரீராஜராஜன் மரக்காலால் முமுப்பதின் கலத்துக்கு ஆண்டு வரிநாள் முன்னூற்றுபதினுக்கு நெல்லு பதினாயிரத்து ஐஞ்ஞாற்றிற.

திருவாய் மொழிந்தருள, நம்மூர் பரிபாலிக்கின்ற காளி ஏகாம்ரநாரும் இருக்க இப்பரிசு செய்தோம் மஹாசபையோம் கரைபோந்து பணித்து ஸ்ரீசுந்த சோழச் செரி வெண்ணிச்செட்டு கணஸ்வாமி கிரவித்தப் பணியால் ஸ்ரீ செம்பியன்மாதேவிச்சேரி மத்வஸ்தன் திருவேங்கடமான கருணாகர ப்ரியனேன். இதன்மம் தென்சேரி ஸ்ரீவீரநாராயணச் சதுர்வேதிமங்கலத்தார்ரசைக.

Conclusion

Ennayiram is beautiful. How this name come to this village? If you ask the villagers, eight thousand Jains were **washed** here. That is why the name Nennayaram is said to have been fixed. But if you dig a little, you will find that it is not true. This Chittoor was popularly known as Paruthikollai during the Pallava rule. Also, the owner Ramanuja woke up in a cotton gin on his way from Sriperumbudur to Thiruvakindhapuram. The Jains who stayed there and argued with him were defeated. According to the agreement they are ready to wash. The supreme possessor made all the Jainas into Antanaras. Eight thousand people were reborn that day. The cotton mill itself came to be known as Ennairam. This is the story of the origin of the Brahmin class called Ashta Sakasram. Jain ablutions In the matter of 'Jain ablutions'. Ennairam Jains who lived in Madurai belonged to Ennairam near Villupuram. They were the ones who composed Naladiyar. Some of them may have been washed away because of the wrong medicine given to the king. That is what has been recorded in the literature as 8000 Jamanas Kavikalamegam. He was born in this Ennairam village. This is confirmed by the following text found in a 17th century inscription found at Kanchipuram.

மண்ணில் இருவர் மணவாளர், மண்ணளந்த
கண்ணன் அவன், இவன்பேர்காள முகில்- கண்ணன்
அவனுக்கூர் எண்ணில் அணியரங்கம் ஒன்றே
இவனுக்கூர் எண்ணாயிரம்.

Animal Fossil In the early 1990s, during construction of a new hospital in the eight thousand, fragments of an animal (elephant) bone were found, petrified. These have been sent for expert review. Through this, it is known that the village of Ennairamgram is historical.

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